

Influence of Strategic Human Capital Development on Implementation of Homa Bay County Integrated Development Plan

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Abstract:- Strategic leadership is an essential ingredient in the meticulous development and implementation of County Integrated Development Plan (CIDP). Poor Implementation is a concern of stakeholders involved in implementation of devolution since the National Government continues to increase resources as shown. Reports from various government agencies mandated to audit and assess the execution of CIDPs and general service delivery have raised queries on the manner the execution of CIDPs. So far the National Government has put controls such as; Legislative control through Public Accounts Committee (PAIC) both at the Senate and County Assemblies, Executive Control such as Effective policy, planning and financial control ,Guidelines are issued regularly by National Treasury prior to commencement of budget in accordance with Sec. 104 of PFM Act,2012, Budget Controls through ensuring compliance with budgetary authorizations and adequate monitoring and reporting capabilities are put in place , Auditor General Levels of Expenditure Control through Detection of irregularities. The past studies linking implementation to strategic leadership focused majorly on variables such as innovation, institutionalization, culture, policies and procedure, organization structures and resource allocation as possible factors for implementation. This study sought to identify the influence of strategic human capital development on implementation of Homa Bay County Integrated Development Plan. The study was guided by upper echelons, resource based and stakeholder theories. It adopted correlational research design, targets 117 respondents consisting of senior and middle level management officers consisting of County Executive Committee Members, chief officers, directors, deputy directors, in Homa-Bay County government and the clerk of the County Assembly. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaire. Cronbach Alpha was used to test instrument reliability at a threshold value of 0.7 while content validity was used to test instrument validity. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed for analysis and data using the SPSS software for data analysis. The findings were presented using tables. Results indicated that strategic human capital development ($\beta=.231, p<.05$) has a positive influence on implementation of county integrated development plan. It was concluded that strategic human capital development has a significant influence on the implementation of CIDP and hence recommended for their improvement. This study opens up research gaps in this subject area and also serves as a relevant source of reference for further research in strategic leadership and implementation of county

development programs. Policy makers who are the regulators and the government can benefit from this study as results from this study may assist them to ascertain whether there is any increased implementation of County Integrated Development Plans that can openly be credited to strategic leadership.

Keywords:- Strategic, Human Capital Development, Implementation, County Integrated Development Plan.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human capital is the most valuable asset in the organization and useful resource for effective implementation of strategy hence strategic Leaders should involve the employees in implementation of the plans (Rhine & Hunger, 2012). Pournasir (2013) also notes that there is also lack of proper human capital development in Iran, where human resource motivation is important to the success of a strategy. Recent evidence shows that human capital, entailing factors such as staff training & skill development, career advancement, compensation and benefits, development of social capital and ethical practices can highly improve implementation of development plans.

A few studies that have sought the relationship between human capital development and implementation of development plans include Chigozie and Onyia (2018) who established that learning and development motivated employees and boosted their commitment to a firm, Ngereri (2019) and Abdi (2015) who found that among factors that affected strategic implementation was human resource. Costley (2017) established that human capital development positively contributed to implementation of strategic plans while Halidu (2015) found that learning and development enhanced workers technical abilities hence contributing to sustainable implementation of strategic plans in Nigeria. Others studies, Nzube and Bundi (2016) and Odhong' and Omolo (2015) also found that human capital development practices have a positive impact on performance of banks.

It is clear from the aforementioned studies that there is a relationship between human resource development and implementation of development plans. However, most of these studies are scanty in content, in that, whereas some indicate a positive influence of human capital development on implementation of strategic plan, Ngereri (2019), Abdi (2015), Costley (2017), they do not exhaust all the constructs under human resource development such as career development, compensation and ethical practices. Most of the studies are confined to training and development. It is also noted that the application of integrated development plans as an outcome is weak, with

inadequate articulation of underlying constructs. Instead, in some of the studies, Nzuve and Bundi (2016) and Odhong' & Omolo (2015), the outcome subject or implementation of development plans deviates to general performance, and more so in the banking sector. Adequate study on the effect of human capital development on implementation of integrated county development plan is thus timely for Homa Bay County.

In Africa, examples of countries where devolution has been successfully adopted entails such countries as South Africa, Nigeria and Ethiopia (Keraro & Isoe, 2015). Further, Ronald (2002) avers that devolution has worked in different parts of the world such as, US, India, Nigeria, Sweden, UK and South Africa which are economically more developed and have matured democratically. There are varying devolution systems in place, for instance; US, Nigeria and India systems are for federal states while Philippines and Kenya have adopted the local government system of devolution. In Kenya Psiwa (2016) revealed that financial-related challenges, human resource-related challenges, communication challenges, leadership-related challenges, national government policy and legislations and organization culture of a county government affect implementation of CIDP. K. S. (2019) also established other Challenges Facing Implementation of County Integrated Development plan were internal conflicts, stakeholder involvement, resource allocation and political situation. This is in the wake of devolution of the national government to county government in an art to streamline service delivery and distribution of resources in Kenya. Countries like Britain, Germany, United States of America, Canada and Australia adopted devolution.

Homa Bay County Government is currently implementing the second County Integrated Development Plan (2018-2022). In preparation and execution of the aforementioned plan, the county government makes references to national government aspirations and strategic direction provided by vision 2030, governors manifesto, the first CIDP, Homa Bay County development profile, strategic urban development plan for Homa Bay Municipality, MTF consultations and reports of the public participation. However, according to the auditor general report on budget review and implementation, dated 17th March, 2019 there is poor planning, lack of proper public participation and lack of oversight by the County assemblies as some factors effecting implementation of development projects in the county government. In line with this, the county government needs to put emphasis on implementation of the CIDP which is a five-year primary strategic plan around which a county's development agenda and all other planning documents are always aligned. It is against these aforementioned situations that the current study seeks to establish the influence of strategic leadership on implementation of county integrated development plan, in Homa Bay County government.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Devolution has worked in different parts of the world such as, US, India, Nigeria, Sweden and UK. In Africa, it is evident in South Africa, Nigeria and Ethiopia. In Kenya devolution was ushered in after the enactment of the 2010 constitution with the expectation of having the most transformative impact of governance, public administration and resource management across all the 47 county governments. Kenya spends substantial amount on equitable share allocation to County Governments and the National Government continues to increase resources as shown in the analysis; In the Financial Year (FY) 2015/2016 Ksh 259.7 billion, FY 2016/2017 Ksh 280.3 billion, FY 2017/2018 Ksh 291.1 billion, FY 2018/2019 Ksh 314 billion, FY 2019/2020 Ksh 335.67 billion, FY 2020/2021 Ksh 316.5 billion and FY 2021/2022 Ksh. 370 billion. This expenditure has however not been reflected on the performance of the Counties which have been marred with a myriad of challenges that has seen a huge outcry over the This expenditure has however not been reflected on the performance of the County governments. Reports from various government agencies mandated to audit and assess the execution of CIDPs and general service delivery have raised queries on the manner the execution of CIDPs. So far the National Government has put controls such as; Legislative control through Public Accounts Committee (PAIC) both at the Senate and County Assemblies, Executive Control such as Effective policy, planning and financial control ,Guidelines are issued regularly by National Treasury prior to commencement of budget in accordance with Sec. 104 of PFM Act,2012, Budget Controls through ensuring compliance with budgetary authorizations and adequate monitoring and reporting capabilities are put in place , Auditor General Levels of Expenditure Control through Detection of irregularities management of county governments, and Homa-bay County Government is no exception. In line with this, the county government needs to put emphasis on implementation of the **2017-2022 CIDP** which is a five-year primary strategic plan around which a county's development agenda and all other planning documents are always aligned. Limited studies have been done linking strategic leadership and implementation of the **2017-2022 CIDP** in county government and yet a lot of resources are spent with the fruits of devolution are yet to be realized. The past studies linking implementation to strategic leadership focused majorly on variables such as innovation, institutionalization, culture, policies and procedure, organization structures and resource allocation as possible factors for implementation. In addition, strategic leadership attributes such as strategic human resource development have been done in private firms and studies on county governments did not link strategic leadership to implementation of county integrated development plan which considered critical factors for strategy implementation. Therefore, there is lack of adequate empirical evidence on effect of strategic leadership on implementation of county integrated development plan. This motivates the study to examine influence of strategic leadership on implementation of county integrated development plans in Homa-Bay County Government.

A. General objective of the study

The general objective of the study was to assess the influence of strategic human capital development on implementation of Homa Bay County integrated development plan.

B. Research hypotheses

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between strategic human capital development and implementation of Homa -Bay County integrated development plan.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

IV. STAKEHOLDER THEORY

R. Edward Freeman is the proponent of stakeholder theory. Although Freeman himself credits several bodies of literature in the development of his approach, including strategic management, corporate planning, systems theory, organization theory, and corporate social responsibility. It depones that, management is required to fulfill their fiduciary duties to the pertinent stakeholders and safeguard their interest and therefore influences the roles of the board.

Further, Reguera, Laffarga, and Fuentes (2011) contended that stakeholder theory focuses on relationship management with group of stakeholders for individual benefits and those groups who require management's attention. Stakeholder theory argue that for companies to survive, it is important for them to manage the network relationships and take care of the interests of its stakeholders, that is suppliers, business partners and employees, and it was also argue that this group of networks.

In this regard, Fields and Keys (2013) also asserted that increasing pressure by shareholder activists, institutional investors and regulators for appointing a diverse board, using the contentions of stakeholder theory; that is, that a more diverse board will have a social heterogeneity and skill mix that will place the company in a better position to connect with various stakeholder groups, hence make a diversified company remain more competitive due to shareholder value.

Chew and Gillan (2006) argue that Stakeholder Theory does not provide single corporate objective, but directs managers to serve many "Masters". They went further to point out that without the clarity of mission provided by a single valued objective function; companies embracing stakeholder theory will experience managerial confusion, conflict, inefficiency and perhaps even competitive failure of the firm or organization. The stakeholder theory focuses on individual whose interests are directly affected by the activities of a firm.

The stakeholder theory therefore informs this study in the sense that strategic leaders in county government must ensure that diverse need of all stakeholders are well represented. The stakeholder of the county government may include and not limited to civic leaders, County Assembly, the supply chain employees and the general public. The county leaders need to incorporate their views to successfully implement strategic plans.

V. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Chigozie and Onyia (2018), assessed the influence of human capital development on organizational performance of manufacturing industries in South-East Nigeria. Based on organization learning theory, the study used explanatory research design and collected data from 358 CEO of the manufacturing firms and distributors. Inferential statistics showed that Learning and development motivated employees and boost their commitment to the firm; the study recommended that organizations should learn continuously, share knowledge, develop and cultivate a learning culture to enable them implement their strategic plans. But the research didn't indicate if there is a relationship between strategic human capital development and implementation of strategic plans, a gap that this study endeavors to fill.

Abdi (2015) studied on strategy implementation challenges in Mombasa County Government. Based onnew public management theory; the resource-based theory and dynamic capability theory, study employed a case study design and targeted a total of 10 chief officers for interview. The results showed that human resource challenges, inadequate financial resources, lack of adequate control and evaluation measures, leadership and poor coordination, ineffective communication, socio cultural factors and political factors affected strategy implementation. However, the sample size was small (10 respondents) thus faces challenges of generalizability of research findings to a wider population.

Costley (2017), assessed the relationship between human capital development and performance of organizations. Based on Human capital theory, transformation leadership theory, the study used descriptive survey design, primary data was collected from 312 middle level managers. Descriptive statistics revealed that most middle level managers were well equipped with requisite skills to enhance organizational performance, however, a further study was recommended to relate top management teams human resource skills and implementation of strategic plans. However, the study was based on descriptive statistics which are less powerful compared to inferential statistics, a gap that was filled by this study.

Halidu (2015) studied on impact of learning and development on employees' productivity in select Nigerian universities. Based on human capital theory, data was collected from 108 top management team in the sampled universities. Both descriptive and inferential statistics showed that learning and development initiatives enhance workers technical abilities and skills to endure contemporary challenges; and considers learning and development and valuable tool for enhancing and sustaining employee's productivity. A further study was recommended to link human resource development and strategy implementation; a gap that was addressed by this study.

Nzuve and Bundi (2016) studied on the impact human capital development practices on performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Based on dynamic capability theory and correlational study design, the study utilized secondary data from 39 established commercial banks. The study based on secondary data analysis found that human capital development practices have a positive impact on performance of commercial banks in Kenya in relation to both return on assets and turnover growth. However, the study was based in commercial banks and not county government which too needs human capital development to implement strategic plans; thus, the need for this study.

Odhong' and Omolo (2015) examined the role human capital development plays on performance in Kenyan pharmaceutical firms. Based on human capital theories, descriptive data was collected and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Both descriptive and inferential analysis showed that a significant positive relationship between human capital development and organizational performance; but recommended a further study to link human capital development and strategic plans implementation, a gap that was filled by this study.

From the reviewed studies on the influence of human capital development and strategic implementation, Chigozie and Onyia (2018), Abdi (2015) and Costley (2017) used descriptive analysis and failed to show the nature of relationship between the variables while Halidu (2015) showed a positive effect of human capital development on strategic implementation. Furthermore, Nzuve and Bundi (2016) used correlational analysis and revealed that human capital development practices have a positive impact on performance whereas Odhong' and Omolo (2015) used both

descriptive and correlational analysis and revealed a positive and significant relationship between the two variables. Besides these studies' results being mixed or conflicting they merely documented human resource management challenges without showing how strategic human capital development impacts on implementation of county strategic plans a gap this study seeks to fill. Furthermore, the studies omitted some of the key variables or constructs of human capital development. There is therefore need to establish the influence of human capital development on implementation of county integrated development plan.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted both Correlational research design and Descriptive research designs which are described by Michele (2014) as a methods for testing relationships between or among variables under study as well as providing in-depth description of study variables respectively. The present study sought to examine the influence of strategic leadership on implementation of county integrated development plan in Homa Bay County government in Kenya and hence correlational research design was the most appropriate. The population consists of 98 senior and middle level management officers of Homa Bay County, which includes County Executive Committee Members, chief officers of all the departments, directors, deputy directors, clerk of the County Assembly and opinion leaders. Since the population is small (less than 100 respondents), a census method was used to involve all targeted respondents because sampling a small population can lead to sampling bias (Kothari, 2007). The study collected primary data from respondents using structured research instrument while a secondary data collection sheet was used to collect integrated financial data from Homa Bay County government finance department. Reliability results showed that strategic communication had a high reliability value ($\alpha=0.79$) followed by implementation of CIDP ($\alpha=0.77$), strategic human capital development ($\alpha=0.76$), strategic vision ($\alpha=0.73$) and finally strategic alignment ($\alpha=0.71$). Content validity was used to validate research instruments. Linear regression and correlation analyses were based on the association between two (or more) variables.

VII. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis was achieved by measuring the respondent's views on the strategic human capital development in Homa Bay county on a five point Likert scale first. The views were later summarized into a mean which was regressed with implementation of CIDP alongside other predictors. Results on overview of strategic human capital development are presented as shown in Table 4.8 using frequency counts, percentages, means and standard deviation.

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
Do you understand how your job contributes to the Implementation of County Integrated Development Plan?	0(0.0)	5(4.85)	0(0.0)	60(58.25)	38(36.89)	4.27	.703
There is a well stipulated human resource development policy for effective human resource management.	0(0.0)	5(4.85)	0(0.0)	51(49.51)	47(45.63)	4.36	.726
Lack of relevant skill effect implementation of County Integrated Development Plan.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	20(19.42)	74(71.84)	9(8.74)	3.89	.522
Leaders plays a role in motivation workers towards achievement of set development plan.	9(8.74)	24(23.3)	29(28.16)	23(22.33)	18(17.48)	3.17	1.222
Staff training and skill development enhances efficiency toward achievement of development plan.	0(0.0)	5(4.85)	15(14.56)	74(71.84)	9(8.74)	3.84	.638
All employees who advance their job-related skills are rewarded in employment scheme in the County government.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	23(22.33)	62(60.19)	18(17.48)	3.95	.632
Employee compensations, benefits and appraisals are carried out in a transparent, and unbiased manner	0(0.0)	14(13.59)	27(26.21)	48(46.6)	14(13.59)	3.60	.889
top leadership in Homa-Bay County government ensures there is equitable human resource development in all departments	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	20(19.42)	59(57.28)	24(23.3)	4.04	.656
Relationship with the people effects service delivery.	0(0.0)	18(17.48)	39(37.86)	31(30.1)	15(14.56)	3.42	.945
Overall mean and standard deviation						3.83	.380

Table 1: Strategic Human Capital Development

From the findings in Table 4.8, majority, 60(58.25) of the respondents agreed that they understand how their job contributes to the Implementation of County Integrated Development Plan, which was also confirmed by a mean and standard deviation (M=4.27, SD=.703). Majority, 51(49.51) of the respondents, agreed that there is a well stipulated human resource development policy for effective human resource management, which was further affirmed by a high mean (M=4.36, SD=.726) while 74(71.84%) indicated that lack of relevant skill has an effect on implementation of County Integrated Development Plan (M=3.89, SD=.522).

From the findings, it is clear that leaders play a very small role in motivating workers towards achieving of set development plan (M=3.17, SD=1.22), although there was neutral response by majority of the respondents, 29(28.16). The findings further indicates that staff training and skill development enhances efficiency toward achievement of development plan (M=3.84, SD=.638) and was agreed by majority, 74(71.84%). Moreover, according to majority of the respondents, 62(60.19%), all employees who advance

their job-related skills are rewarded in employment scheme in the County government (M=3.95, SD=.632) while employees employee compensations, benefits and appraisals are carried out in a transparent, and unbiased manner as highly rated (M=3.60, SD=.889), and confirmed by majority, 48(46.6%) who agreed. Fifty nine, that is 57.28% of the respondents indicated that top leadership in Homa-Bay County government ensures there is equitable human resource development in all departments as highly rated (M=4.04, SD=.656) While relationship with the people effects service delivery as indicated by cumulatively 46(44.7%) of the respondents who agreed and strongly agreed. In summary, the findings shows that averagely, strategic human capital development was rated above average (M=3.83, SD=.380) with small variations.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	.903	.430		2.103	.038
	Mean Strategic alignment	.124	.051	.217	2.453	.016
	Strategic human capital development	.103	.037	.231	2.789	.006
	Mean strategic Communication	.262	.097	.245	2.685	.009
	Mean strategic vision	.270	.083	.277	3.236	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Mean of County Integrated Development Plan

Table 2: Effect of Strategic Human Capital Development on ICIDP

The findings in Table 1 shows that there would be a significant constant improvement in the implementation of county integrated development plan even without including model predictors (B=0.903, p<.05). However, all the included model coefficients were found to positively and significantly contribute to the implementation of county integrated development plan. Strategic communication (β=.245, p<.05) had a positive and significant effect on implementation of county integrated development plan.

The objective of the study was achieved by regressing the implementation of county development integrated plan against the strategic human capital development via regression model as indicated in Table 4.4 alongside other predictor variables. The findings revealed that strategic human capital development positively and significantly contributed to implementation of CIDP (β=.231, p<.05). This implies that for every one unit increase in the exercise of strategic human capital development, the implementation of CIDP improves by a magnitude of 0.231 based on the scale used. Further analysis indicates that if the coefficient value is squared, then it explains 5.3% variance in the implementation of the county integrated development plan. These results are in line with the previous findings by Abdi (2015), Chigozie and Onyia (2018), Costley (2017) among others who also established some link between strategic human capital development and strategic implementation.

Based on these findings, the null hypothesis which stated that “H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between strategic human capital development and implementation of Homa -Bay County integrated development plan” was rejected and an alternative hypothesis adopted as “H₀₄: There is a significant relationship between strategic human capital development and implementation of Homa -Bay County integrated development plan” It was thus concluded that strategic human capital development has a positive and significant influence on implementation of county integrated development plan.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings indicate that the county carried out good communication and had a good communication system although with slightly small hitches. Following the results of the influence of the strategic communication on the implementation of the county integrated development plan, the study established that there was a positive influence. From the findings, strategic communication is in place in HomaBay county. This means that that leadership is doing its best to ensure that therefore is flow of communication.

As such, there is an improvement in the implementation of the county integrated development plan. Therefore it was concluded that strategic communication improves the implementation of the county integrated development plan in Homa Bay county.Finally, the study recommends that strategic communication should be further improved to ensure good flow of information in the county. This will ensure that strategic communication improves the implementation of county integrated development plan. The study recommends that studies be carried out on the differences in strategic human capital development elements and their effects explored on performance of the county employees

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